

A Gold-aptamer nanoconjugate for the detection of thrombin, a potential biomarker of AD

Tzekaki Eleni, Post Doctoral Researcher, Laboratory of Biochemistry, Department of Chemistry, A.U.Th., Center for Interdisciplinary Research and Innovation, Laboratory of Neurodegenerative Diseases (LND), etzekaki@chem.auth.gr

Katsipis Georgios, Post Doctoral Researcher, Katsiphs.g1@gmail.com

Kazeli Kostantina, PhD Student, kazeli.konstantina@gmail.com

Makridis Antonis, Post Doctoral Researcher, anmakrid@physics.auth.gr

Aggelakeris Makis, Professor, agelaker@auth.gr

Pantazaki Anastasia, Professor, natasa@chem.auth.gr

Although many therapies for confronting Alzheimer's disease (AD) have proven inadequate, the key to combating the disease may lie in its early diagnosis. This relies on detecting proteins of high importance, which have gained prominence in the biomedical field—one of which is thrombin. Thrombin has been suggested as a possible pathological mediator in AD, as it is associated with the characteristic hallmarks of AD pathology. It has been found in senile plaques and neurofibrillary tangles. Furthermore, levels of thrombin and its receptor, Protease-activated receptor-1 (PAR-1), the first member of the PARs family, found during the process of identifying GPCR (G protein-coupled receptors) that mediate thrombin signal pathway in both human and hamster cells, are elevated in AD. In most diagnostic applications, specific protein recognition is often facilitated by antibodies. However, aptamers—promising small DNA/RNA molecules—are emerging as potential alternatives to antibodies. Given thrombin's role as a potential biomarker for AD diagnosis, thrombin aptamers were used to bioconjugate thrombin onto gold nanoparticle-based scaffolds. A freezing-directed protocol was proposed to bind the DNA aptamer to gold nanoparticles. The thrombin aptamer used was TBA1. Thawing the aptamer-AuNPs after overnight incubation at -20°C was sufficient to produce stable aptamer-gold nanoconjugates.

4 key words

Aptamer

Thrombin

Gold nanoparticles

Early diagnosis